

Deliverable RM3

Document with the technical specifications concerning the details of the wearable device

Document history

Version	Date	Description	Authors
V.1.0	22-01-2023	INDIP specifications	M. Caruso, A. Cereatti
V.2.0	23-01-2023	TED specifications	M. Canonico

Table of contents

1. Introduction.....	3
2. INDIP system	4
2.1. System overview	4
2.2. INDIP system kit – Overview	6
2.3. Main components	11
2.4. Digital mobility outcomes.....	15
3. TED system.....	18
3.1. System description	18
3.2. Technical specifications.....	18

1. Introduction

This document describes the main technical features of the INDIP and TED devices.

2. INDIP system

2.1. System overview

INertial module with Distance Sensors and Pressure insoles (INDIP) is a multi-sensor system which integrates an inertial module, up to two distance sensors and up to one pressure insole. The block diagram of the INDIP system full configuration is reported in Figure 1. The inertial module includes an ultra-low-power microcontroller unit (MCU), a magneto-inertial measurement unit (MIMU → triaxial accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer), a flash storage, and a wireless connectivity (Bluetooth LE). Each distance sensor integrates an infrared time-of-flight distance sensor that can be connected to the inertial module by cable. The pressure insole consists of sixteen force sensing resistor elements and can be connected to the inertial module using a zif connector. The *raw output data* include:

- Linear acceleration: Raw and calibrated XYZ measurements (up to ± 16 g);
- Angular velocity: Raw and calibrated XYZ measurements (up to ± 2000 dps);
- Local magnetic field: Raw and calibrated XYZ measurements (up to ± 50 gauss);
- Distance: Calibrated distance (up to 600 mm);
- Pressure: Output voltage for each sensing element (0 to V_{DD});

Figure 1: Block diagram.

Hardware specifications

<u>Magneto-Inertial Module</u>			
MCU		Storage	
Architecture	ARM® 32-bit Cortex®-M4 CPU with FPU	FLASH MEMORY	
Operating frequency	up to 80 MHz	Size	128 MB
Flash memory size	256 kB	Temperature range	-40 to +85°C
Internal RAM size	64 kB	BLUETOOTH	
Temperature range	-40 to +85 °C	Standard	Bluetooth v4.1
		Range	≈10 m

<p><i>Power supply</i></p> <hr/> <p>BATTERY</p> <hr/> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>Type</td> <td>Rechargeable Lithium Ion Polymer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Nominal voltage</td> <td>3.7 V</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Nominal capacity</td> <td>155 mAh</td> </tr> </table> <hr/> <p><i>Connectivity</i></p> <hr/> <p>USB</p> <hr/> <table border="0"> <tr> <td>Standard</td> <td>USB 2.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Connector</td> <td>Micro USB (type B)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Additional feature</td> <td>INPUT for external synchronization</td> </tr> </table>	Type	Rechargeable Lithium Ion Polymer	Nominal voltage	3.7 V	Nominal capacity	155 mAh	Standard	USB 2.0	Connector	Micro USB (type B)	Additional feature	INPUT for external synchronization	<table border="0"> <tr> <td>Transmission rate</td> <td>Up to 560 kbps with SPP / 250 kbps with iAP service</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Features</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports master and slave modes • Multiple roles supported simultaneously </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Temperature range</td> <td>-40 to +85 °C</td> </tr> </table>	Transmission rate	Up to 560 kbps with SPP / 250 kbps with iAP service	Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports master and slave modes • Multiple roles supported simultaneously 	Temperature range	-40 to +85 °C						
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Temperature range -40 to +85 °C			
<u>Distance sensor</u>		<u>Pressure insole</u>	
DISTANCE and AMBIENT LIGHT (up to 3)		PRESSURE INSOLE	
Measurement range	0-200 / 0-400 / 0-600 mm dynamically selectable full scale	No. sensing elements	16
Ambient range	<1 Lux up to 100 kLux	EU Size	36-37 to 46-47
Sensitivity	±1 / ±2 / ±3 mm	Output data rate	100 Hz
Output data rate	up to 50 Hz		
Temperature range	-20 to +70 °C		

2.2. INDIP system kit – Overview

Figure 2: INDIP kit.

2.2.1. Carrying case

All the INDIP system components are supplied in an aluminium carrying case (L460 × W330 × H150 mm).

Figure 3: Carrying case.

2.2.2. INDIP units and INDIP calibration case

The INDIP units integrates a tri-axial accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer and are provided in a custom 3D printed case that allows an easy alignment of the INDIP units along the X⁺, X⁻, Y⁺, Y⁻, Z⁺, Z⁻ axis.

Figure 4: INDIP units and INDIP calibration case.

2.2.3. Clips and VELCRO straps

Two different options for securing the INDIP units on the subject are provided:

Clips
(only for foot mounting)

Figure 5: Clips.

VELCRO straps
(head, hand, lower back, ankle, and foot mounting)

Figure 6: Velcro straps.

2.2.4. Hub USB and USB- μ USB cables

A 4-port hub USB and four USB- μ USB cable are provided to charge and read data from the INDIP units.

Figure 7: Hub USB and USB- μ USB cables.

2.2.5. Pressure and leather insoles

The pressure insole, consisting of sixteen force sensitive resistor elements, allows the measurement of the foot to ground contacts. In addition, leather insoles are provided and recommended for reducing the movement of the pressure insoles when recording an acquisition (leather insoles should be positioned between the foot and the shoe).

Pressure insoles

(EU 36/37, 40/41, or 42/43)

Figure 8: Pressure insoles.

Leather insoles

(EU 36/37, 38/39, 40/41, 42/43, 44/45)

Figure 9: Leather insoles.

A tool for helping the connection/disconnection of the pressure insole to/from the INDIP unit is also provided.

Pressure insole tool

Figure 10: Pressure insole tool.

Opening of the pressure insole connector on the INDIP unit

Figure 11: Connection of the pressure insole to the INDIP unit.

2.2.6. Distance sensors and cables

Distance sensors, connected to the INDIP units via a 30cm cable, allow the measurement of the distance between the distance sensor and anything in front of it within 20, 40, or 60 cm (range user-selectable).

Figure 12: Distance sensors and cables.

2.2.7. External synchronization cable

The INDIP system supports the synchronization with an external equipment in two modes:

- Output synchronization: when the INDIP system begins recording data, it will output a signal to external equipment when the recording starts by exploiting the ID pin of the μ USB.
- Input synchronization: the INDIP system will immediately begin recording when it receives a signal from external equipment on the ID pin of the μ USB.

External synchronization cable

Figure 13: μ USB-BNC/RCA cable.

Example of the synchronization setup with an external equipment

Figure 14: Hardware connection between Vicon (master) and INDIP (slave) systems.

2.3. Main components

2.3.1. INDIP unit

Figure 15: INDIP unit.

Figure 16: INDIP unit ID (e.g., "INDIP#001").

LED description

INDIP State	Red LED	Green LED	Blue LED	Operating State
OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF	SHUTDOWN
ON	ON	OFF	OFF	ERROR
ON	ON	OFF	ON (Blinking every 2s)	IDLE & Battery level <10%
ON	ON	ON (Pulsing)	ON (Blinking every 2s)	System in charge & Battery level < 10%
ON	ON (Pulsing)	OFF	ON (Blinking every 2s)	IDLE & 10% < Battery level < 30%
ON	ON (Pulsing)	ON (Pulsing)	ON (Blinking every 2s)	System in charge & 10% < Battery level < 30%
ON	ON (Blinking every 0.4s)	ON (Pulsing)	ON (Blinking every 2s)	IDLE & System in charge & setTime not performed
ON	OFF	ON (Pulsing)	ON (Blinking every 2s)	IDLE & System in charge & setTime performed
ON	OFF	ON (Pulsing)	ON	READING data

ON	ON	ON (Pulsing)	ON	READING data & Low battery level
ON	ON (Blinking every 0.4s)	ON	ON (Blinking every 2s)	IDLE & Charge completed & setTime not performed
ON	OFF	ON	ON (Blinking every 2s)	IDLE & Charge completed & setTime performed
ON	OFF	OFF	ON (Blinking every 0.4s)	STREAMING
ON	OFF	OFF	ON	RECORDING

2.3.2. Pressure insole

Figure 17: Pressure insole.

Figure 18: Pressure insole ID (e.g., "PI#R001").

Size: 36/37 EU, 38/39 EU, 40/41 EU, 42/43 EU, 44/45 EU, 46/47 EU for both Left and Right Sides.

2.3.3. Distance sensor

Figure 19: Distance sensor.

Figure 20: Distance sensor ID (e.g., "DS#001").

Note: To be recognized, the distance sensor must be connected to the INDIP unit only when the INDIP unit is switched off.

2.4. Digital mobility outcomes

Category	Outcome	Unit	Description
Overall	StrideFrequency	strides/min	Average stride frequency in the WB ¹ $\left(\frac{\sum_{k=1}^{\text{NumberStrides}} \frac{60}{\text{Stride_duration}_k}}{\text{NumberStrides}} \right)$
	Cadence	steps/min	Cadence $(2 \cdot \text{StrideFrequency})$
	WalkingSpeed	m/s	Walking speed $\left(\frac{\sum_{k=1}^{\text{NumberStrides}} \text{Stride_Speed}}{\text{NumberStrides}} \right)$
	AverageStrideLength	m	The average stride length over all detected strides
	NumberStrides		Number of identified strides - linked to number of initial contacts
	Turning_Flag	FLAG	Indicates if curvilinear portions are present (1) or not (0)
	TerminationReason		Identify why a WB ¹ has been terminated ('Pause', 'SharpTurn', 'InclineWalking')
	ElevationChange	m	Difference between the minimal and maximal height or elevation for the complete gait sequence detected
	NumberInitialContacts		Based on the correct identification of final contact events
	AverageStrideDuration	s	Average stride time across the WB ¹
	AverageStepDuration	s	Average step time across the WB ¹
	AverageSwingDuration	s	Average swing time across the WB ¹
	AverageStanceDuration	s	Average stance time across the WB ¹
	AverageTurnDuration	s	Average turn duration across the WB ¹
	AverageMaxTurnAngle	deg/s	Average of max turning angle achieved in the WB ¹
	Break	Break_Start	s
Break_End		s	Termination time of each break
Break_Duration		s	Duration of each break
Break_Number			Number of breaks
Turn	Turn_Start	s	Start time of each turn (relative to the start of the recording)
	Turn_End	s	Termination time of each turn (relative to the start of the recording)
	Turn_Duration	s	Duration of each turn
	Turn_Number		Number of performed turns
	Turn_Angle	deg	Angle (magnitude) of each turn
	Turn_NumberStrides		Number of strides performed for each turn
	Turn_AngularVelocity	deg/s	Angular velocity for each sample of the turn phase
	Turn_PeakAngularVelocity	deg/s	Maximum angular velocity measured for each turn
	Turn_MeanAngularVelocity	deg/s	Mean angular velocity measured for each turn
	Turn_Length	m	Path travelled during the turn
Turn_NormAngle	deg/(s*m)	Normalized turn angle (per path length) $\left(\frac{\text{Turn_Angle}}{\text{Turn_Length}} \right)$	

	Turn_NormAngularVelocity	deg/(s*m)	Normalized turn mean velocity (per path length) $\left(\frac{Turn_MeanAngularVelocity}{Turn_Length}\right)$
	Turn_Smoothness	AU	Average smoothness of the turn (Turn_Angular Velocity)
	Turning_SharpTurn_Flag	FLAG	Indicates, among the turns, the sharp ones (1)
Incline	Incline_Start	s	Start time of each incline walking (relative to the start of the recording)
	Incline_End	s	Termination time of each incline walking (relative to the start of the recording)
	Incline_Duration	s	Duration of each incline walking
	Incline_Number		Number of detected incline walking
	Incline_NumberStrides		Number of strides for each incline walking
	Incline_PositiveElevation	m	Positive elevation for each incline walking (assessed as the overall positive elevation observed for each elevation walking)
	Incline_NegativeElevation	m	Negative elevation for each incline walking (assessed as the overall negative elevation observed for each elevation walking)
	Stride_InitialContacts		Initial contacts that identify each stride ([ICstart, ICend])
	Stride_Duration	s	Stride or gait cycle duration (time elapsed between consecutive initial contacts of the same foot)
	Stride_Length	m	Length, displacement covered within stride cycles
Stride_Height	m	Vertical foot displacement covered within stride cycles	
Stride_Speed	m/s	Stride or gait cycle velocity $\left(\frac{Stride_Length}{Stride_Duration}\right)$	
Stance_Duration	s	Stance phase duration for each stride (initiated by an initial contact and terminates with a final contact of the same foot)	
Swing_Duration	s	Swing phase duration for each stride (time elapsed between a final contact of the current footfall and the following initial contact of the next footfall on the same foot)	
Stance_Length	m	Length, displacement covered within the stance phases	
Swing_Length	m	Length, displacement covered within the swing phases	
Stance_Speed	m/s	Velocity of each stance phase $\left(\frac{Stance_Length}{Stance_Duration}\right)$	
Swing_Speed	m/s	Velocity of each swing phase $\left(\frac{Swing_Length}{Swing_Duration}\right)$	
Stride and step	SingleSupport_Duration	s	Single support (or single limb support phase) duration for each stride (time elapsed between the final contact of the current footfall to the initial contact of the next footfall of the same foot)
	DoubleSupport_Duration	s	Double support (or dual limb support phase) duration for each stride (amount of time spent with both feet on the ground during a gait cycle)
	InitialContact_Event	s	Time instant at which each initial contact is performed (initial contact events, both for the left and right limbs)

InitialContact_LeftRight		Indicate 'Left' or 'Right' indicating the side with which the relevant IC is performed
FinalContact_Event	s	Time instant at which each final contact is performed (final contact events, both for the left and right limbs)
FinalContact_LeftRight		Indicate 'Left' or 'Right' indicating the side with which the relevant FC is performed
Step_Duration	s	Step cycle duration (time elapsed from an initial contact of one foot to consecutive one of the contralateral foot)

¹ A walking bout (WB) is a walking sequence containing at least two consecutive strides of both feet (e.g., R-L-R-L-R-L or L-R-L-R-L-R). Start and end of a WB are determined by a resting period or any other activity (non-walking period). The initial step of a WB follows a non-walking period and the final step precedes the next non-walking period.

3. TED system

3.1. System description

The TED device is an advanced technological device developed by 4Sec Ltd, equipped with an accelerometer, gyroscope, and GPS capable of detecting a high number of samples per second related to gravitational acceleration and angular velocity on all three axes (x, y, and z), as well as position data. The device has been designed to adapt to the biological variability of each individual. In this sense, it is fully programmable, and its performance is optimized for each individual. The process of adaptation and improvement of the quality of produced information is continuous. The collected data is sent to the Cloud collection system, both continuously (monitoring of the function of interest) and on occasions of events inserted into the monitoring plan (such as falls or the risk of falling). The data collected on the Cloud system are then processed by Machine Learning systems capable of extracting knowledge and learning elements from the device data, using the most modern machine learning techniques.

3.2. Technical specifications

3.2.1. Design features

The design features essentially encompass two main aspects:

- Functional (acquisition parameters, sensors, power supply, etc.)
- Ergonomics and wearability (shape, weight, IP rating, material compatibility, etc.)

3.2.2. Functional features

Functional features pertain to a series of non-vital parameters acquired through sensors installed on the electronic boards. An important aspect of patient monitoring relates to the localization and control of mobility and stability to detect potential falls and potentially risky situations. To achieve this, the device is equipped with a GPS module, an accelerometer, and a vectorial gyroscope; the sensors can also detect phenomena such as tremors and hyperkinesias. A buzzer for auditory notifications + LED is present.

The electrical autonomy exceeds 5 hours and can reach up to 72 hours depending on usage conditions. The device includes a rechargeable lithium polymer battery with a voltage of 3.7V and a capacity of 2000 mAh, nominally corresponding to a maximum total energy of 7.4 Wh. The charge duration depends heavily on how the hardware resources of the device are managed via the firmware. The device is equipped with a connector for SIM card and SD card. Battery charging is done via a micro USB connector.

3.2.3. Ergonomics and wearability

To facilitate wearability, the device is positioned using a plastic support attached to the patient's belt with sliding insertion. Applying the device to the patient's body is quick and simple.

3.2.4. System architecture

The system architecture is based on the ESP32-WROVER-E module, which combines MCU WiFi-BT-BLE functionalities. The following table outlines the device characteristics.

MCU Module:

Categories	Items	Specifications
Certification	RF certification	FCC/CE-RED/SRRC
Test	Reliability	HTOL/HTSL/uHAST/TCT/ESD
Wi-Fi	Protocols	802.11 b/g/n (802.11n up to 150 Mbps) A-MPDU and A-MSDU aggregation and 0.4 μ s guard interval support
	Frequency range	2412 ~ 2484 MHz
Bluetooth	Protocols	Bluetooth v4.2 BR/EDR and BLE specification
	Radio	NZIF receiver with -97 dBm sensitivity
		Class-1, class-2 and class-3 transmitter
		AFH
Audio	CVSD and SBC	
Hardware	Module interfaces	SD card, UART, SPI, SDIO, I ² C, LED PWM, Motor PWM, I ² S, IR, pulse counter, GPIO, capacitive touch sensor, ADC, DAC, Two-Wire Automotive Interface (TWAI [®] , compatible with ISO11898-1)
	On-chip sensor	Hall sensor
	Integrated crystal	40 MHz crystal
	Integrated SPI flash	4 MB
	Integrated PSRAM	8 MB
	Operating voltage/Power supply	3.0 V ~ 3.6 V
	Minimum current delivered by power supply	500 mA
	Recommended operating temperature range	-40 °C ~ 85 °C
	Package size	(18.00±0.15) mm × (31.40±0.15) mm × (3.30±0.15) mm
	Moisture sensitivity level (MSL)	Level 3

Figure 21: TED technical specifications

LTE Communication Module:

The communication module used is the A7672xx produced by SIMCom, with the following technical specifications (European Version A7672E).

Product	A7672S	A7672E	A7672SA
Form Factor	LCC+LGA	LCC+LGA	LCC+LGA
Dimensions(mm)	24.0*24.0*2.4	24.0*24.0*2.4	24.0*24.0*2.4
Frequency Bands	LTE-FDD	B1/B3/B5/B8	B1/B2/B3/B4/B5/B7/B8/B28/B66
	LTE-TDD	B34/B38/B39/B40/B41	
	GSM	900/1800MHz	900/1800MHz
Temperature	-40°C ~ +85°C	-40°C ~ +85°C	-40°C ~ +85°C
Electrical Features			
Supply Voltage(V)	3.4~ 4.2	3.4~ 4.2	3.4~ 4.2
Power	LTE TBD	TBD	TBD
Consumption (mA)	GSM,BS_PA_MFRMS=2 TBD	TBD	TBD
Data Transfer			
LTE(Mbps)	10(DL)/5(UL)	10(DL)/5(UL)	10(DL)/5(UL)
GPRS/EDGE(Kbps)	236.8(DL)/236.8(UL)	236.8(DL)/236.8(UL)	236.8(DL)/236.8(UL)
Software Features			
Protocol	TCP/IP/IPV4/IPV6/Multi-PDP/FTP/FTPS /HTTP/HTTPS/DNS	TCP/IP/IPV4/IPV6/Multi-PDP/FTP/FTPS /HTTP/HTTPS/DNS	TCP/IP/IPV4/IPV6/Multi-PDP/FTP/FTPS /HTTP/HTTPS/DNS
TLS	•	•	•
MQTT	•	•	•
File System	•	•	•
Audio Record/Play	0	0	0
TTS	•	•	•
LBS	•	•	•
FOTA	•	•	•
Android RIL	Android 5.0/6.0/7.0/8.0/9.0	Android 5.0/6.0/7.0/8.0/9.0	Android 5.0/6.0/7.0/8.0/9.0
USB Driver	Microsoft Windows 7/8/10 Linux/Android	Microsoft Windows 7/8/10 Linux/Android	Microsoft Windows 7/8/10 Linux/Android
WWAN (RNDIS)	•	•	•
ECM	•	•	•
Embedded AT	0	0	0
Firmware Upgrade	USB/FOTA	USB/FOTA	USB/FOTA
Interfaces			
SIM Card	1.8V/3.0V	1.8V/3.0V	1.8V/3.0V
UART	•	•	•
USB	•	•	•
PCM	0	0	0
ADC	•	•	•
GPIO	•	•	•
I2C	•	•	•
GNSS	0	0	0
BLE	0	0	0
Certification			
Certification		CE-RED*/RoHS*/ REACH*	Anatel*/RoHS*/ REACH*

Figure 22: technical specifications of the LTE communication module.

NOTES:

The WiFi-BT-BLE and LTE A7672E MCU modules used in the device individually comply with CE directives on Radiofrequency.

Accelerometer and Gyroscope Modules:

The gyroscope/accelerometer is based on the LSM6DS3TR-C module produced by ST.

Symbol	Parameter	Test conditions	Min.	Typ. ⁽¹⁾	Max.	Unit
LA_FS	Linear acceleration measurement range			±2		g
				±4		
				±8		
				±16		
G_FS	Angular rate measurement range			±125		dps
				±250		
				±500		
				±1000		
LA_So	Linear acceleration sensitivity ⁽²⁾	FS = ±2		0.061		mg/LSB
		FS = ±4		0.122		
		FS = ±8		0.244		
		FS = ±16		0.488		
G_So	Angular rate sensitivity ⁽²⁾	FS = ±125		4.375		mdps/LSB
		FS = ±250		8.75		
		FS = ±500		17.50		
		FS = ±1000		35		
		FS = ±2000		70		
LA_SoDr	Linear acceleration sensitivity change vs. temperature ⁽³⁾	from -40° to +85°		±0.01		%/°C
G_SoDr	Angular rate sensitivity change vs. temperature ⁽³⁾	from -40° to +85°		±0.007		%/°C
LA_TyOff	Linear acceleration zero-g level offset accuracy ⁽⁴⁾			±40		mg
G_TyOff	Angular rate zero-rate level ⁽³⁾			±3		dps
LA_OffDr	Linear acceleration zero-g level change vs. temperature ⁽³⁾			±0.5		mg/°C
G_OffDr	Angular rate typical zero-rate level change vs. temperature ⁽³⁾			±0.05		dps/°C
Rn	Rate noise density in high-performance mode ⁽⁵⁾			5		mdps/√Hz
RnRMS	Gyroscope RMS noise in normal/low-power mode ⁽⁶⁾			75		mdps

Figure 23: range of the sensors embedded in the TED device.

Figure 24: symbolic view of the inertial module.

Figure 25: overall Electronic Board View:

PROJECT:	4sec Tracker
DRAWING TITLE:	IN
DRAWN BY:	
SHEET: 3 OF 3	STATUS:
DATE:	05/01/23
REVISION:	

PROJECT: 4sec Tracker	
DRAWING TITLE: Power	
DRAWN BY:	
SHEET: 1 OF 3	STATUS:
DATE: 05/01/23	REVISION:

3.2.5. Plastic case

The casing is made of PA12 using 3D microfusion printing technology. The following figures represent the device in various views. The casing has an IP52 protection rating.

Figure 26: plastic case models.

The following figure illustrates the solution for the wearability of the device.

Figure 27: smart badge overview

Figure 28: exploded components

3.2.6. Device Dimensions:

